

Received: 15th February 2022

Revised: 10th March 2022

Accepted: 20th April 2022

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS AND IMPACT OF INDUSTRIAL EFFLUENTS ON WATER QUALITY OF DIFFERENT SOURCES**PUSHPA YADAV, SOUVANIK TALUKDAR, SOMA SHARMA AND ANOOP YADAV****ABSTRACT**

Industrial effluents entering into a water body directly or indirectly represent a heavy source of water pollution. It affects the water quality and competing demand on limiting water resources. A study of four water samples, collected from bore well, Sewage Treatment Plant (STP), canal, and pond of industrial area of Bawal, was carried out to analyse the impact of industrial growth on water quality. The samples were analysed for physiochemical parameters, like pH, electrical conductivity (EC), Total Dissolved Solid (TDS), Total suspended Solids (TSS), Total Solid (TS), nitrates, phosphates, alkalinity, and minerals, like iron (Fe), magnesium (Mg), potassium (K) etc. Results show that STP water has very high EC (1778 $\mu\text{s}/\text{cm}$), a low concentration of K, and found rich in Mg and Fe contents. Ground water has very low EC (6.94 $\mu\text{s}/\text{cm}$), very high TDS (3800 mg/L) and TS values (3804 mg/L) and found rich in nitrates. Ground water has highest concentration of potassium (51 mg/L), whereas pond water and canal water has not shown presence of potassium, but a low concentration (0.75 mg/L) of K was found in STP water. Iron concentrations were found to follow the order, STP water (2.2 mg/L) > ground water (1.27 mg/L) > canal water (1.00 mg/L) > pond water (0.96 mg/L). Surprisingly all water samples have higher concentration of iron than the permissible limit for drinking purpose but comply with the standard limits for irrigation water. Ground water was found unsafe for drinking purpose and its quality deteriorated and needs further treatments to improve its quality. STP water may be used for irrigation purpose after a proper treatment. Results show that there is direct leaching of contaminants to the ground water through soil which harms the quality of water.

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Water is the imperative and primary requirement of living beings for their survival. Life cannot be imagined without water. A person can remain alive for few days without food but can't survive without water. Population of world has been increasing exponentially year by year but natural resources are present in a limited quantity and humans are consuming these natural resources without having concern about their scarcity. Postel et al has reported that the exigency of water jumped up to six fold between 1900 and 1995, that is greater than two-fold increase in population. Not only India but world is facing paucity of fresh water. Shortage of water is mainly affected by regional water balance, climate, altitude, soil composition, vegetation cover, precipitation, and percolation.¹ Scarcity of fresh water is itself a major problem but polluting the available consumable water has become a gigantic problem. People of some regions of our country are still depends on the open water sources like streams, rivers, lakes, and ponds, which are highly prone to get contamination that may be either natural or anthropogenic. Industries are one of the major consumers of water resources and dominating polluting agencies. A huge amount of water get consumed by several factories for cleaning of floor, dilution, cooling, and various other industrial processes. Waste water is generated from petroleum refineries, steel, paper, and pulp industries, dyeing factories, illegal disposal of pesticides, de-icing agents, and industrial-site drainages. Direct disposal of such waste water pollutes the soil as well as water bodies and ultimately affects the lives of living beings. Organic, inorganic as well as microbiological contamination of water has becomes an alarming issue for the society.³ Referring to United Nations report released on March 22, 2010 on World Water Day, 80% of urban waste in India reaches in the country's rivers, and uncontrolled industrialization across the country without concerning about environment will worsen the problem.⁴ Heavy metals constitutes a hazardous group of pollutants. Their presence in water above the permissible limits make the water unhealthy for drinking as well as for irrigation purpose. According to WHO, scarcity of safe drinking water or polluted water is responsible for about 80% of diseases in the world.(WHO1997) According to Tripathi et al, detergents, domestic sewage, farm manure, gases (e.g., chlorine, ammonia), anions (e.g., sulphide, sulphite, cyanide), metals (e.g., cadmium, zinc, lead), oil and oil dispersants, organic toxic wastes (formaldehydes, phenols) pathogens, pesticides, polychlorinated biphenyls and radionuclides are the major pollutants of water.^{1,5} N Jain et al reported the long term use of post methanation distillery effluents can affect the ground water quality. Nitrate and other toxicants may leaches to ground water by the regular use of PMDE for irrigation. Various organic and inorganic ions get added to the ground water with the use effluents.⁶ However, some studies have shown that the increased values of available N, K, P and exchangeable Na in distillery effluents than the paper mill effluents and control water. Some positive results were found with the use of post methanation effluents in irrigation after proper dilution.⁷

Deverajan et al has interpreted that the controlled and safe use of distillery effluents may reduce the use of fertilizers.⁸ Several studies have been conducted on the assessment of water quality degradation near various industries like glass, paper and pulp, leather, oil refineries, dyeing, steel processing units, and sugar mills in major industrial cities. Decline in water quality has been reported by many researchers. However, many studies have reported the reuse of treated and diluted waste water for irrigation can be a better option. Good nutrient value had been reported in few studies in the treated waste water from industries, but presence of toxic heavy metal is again a serious threat to the environment. Industrial area Bawal comprises many small and large scale industries. Only a handful of reports has been submitted regarding the impact of industrialization in Bawal town on the water quality. In this article we are presenting a study on the effect of industrial growth on nearby water bodies and ground water in Bawal Industrial area.

1.2 METHODS AND MATERIALS

1.2.1 Study Area

Industrial model township Bawal is a large industrial centre developed by Haryana State Industrial and Infrastructure Development Corporation. Its geographical coordinates are 28.5° North and 76.350° East. It is situated near Delhi-Jaipur national highway. Many small and large-scale industries, national and multinational industries are situated here. Area selected for sampling is surrounded by many industries like paper and pulp, paint industry, automobile, steel processes industry, cement industry etc.

1.2.2 Sampling and Methodology

Four water samples were collected from the industrial area of Bawal. Samples from a canal adjacent to the industrial disposed sludge (about 75 meter), from a pond (3 km away from sludge), ground water and STP water were collected in plastic bottles. Sampling bottles were cleaned and dried properly and were rinsed with the target water before sampling. Later the samples were taken to laboratory and filtered with 0.2 micro-meter membrane. Samples were stored in a icebox and analysed for pH, EC, TSS, TDS, TS, nitrates, potassium, phosphate, Mg, Fe and Na. Sodium and potassium was determined by flame photo meter. pH and EC were measured by pH meter and conductivity meter respectively. Phosphate, potassium, and nitrate were measured by following standard methods IS 3025 Part 31, 45, and 34 respectively.

1.3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The water samples were characterised for different physico-chemical parameters and the data is compiled in table 1

Table 1: Physico-chemical water parameters of four sampling site

Parameters	Source I	Source 2	Source 3	Source 4
pH	7.19	8.00	6.78	6.55
EC (µs/cm)	6.94	1778	261	154.4
TDS (mg/L)	3800	1109	168	102
TSS (mg/L)	>5	237	18	14
TS (mg/L)	3804	1346	186	116
Nitrates (mg/L)	42	44	0.68	0.72
Phosphates(mg/L)	75	81	1.3	1.2
Potassium (mg/L)	51	0.75	ND	ND
Magnesium(mg/L)	ND	0.4	ND	ND
Iron (mg/L)	1.27	2.2	1.0	0.96
Sodium (mg/L)	96	182	12	9

Source 1: Ground water, Source 2: Sewage treated plant water, Source 3: Canal water nearby disposed sludge, Source 4: Pond water

Comparative Plots of Water Parameters of Different Sources

Figure 1: pH plots for different water samples

Figure 2: TS plots for different water samples

Figure 3: Na content in water samples

Figure 4: Fe content in water samples

Figure 5: EC Plots in water samples

Figure 6: phosphate content in water samples

Figure 7: Total dissolved solids in water samples

Figure 8: Nitrate content in water samples

1.3.1 PH

pH of all the samples are in range of 6.5-8.0, which comply with the range suggested by WHO for drinking water and FAQ for irrigation water. Water pH were found to follow the order i.e. STP water (8.00) > ground water (7.19) > canal water (6.78) > pond water (6.55). STP water is found alkaline. Lowest pH was recorded in pond water as shown in Table 1 and Fig. 1.

1.3.2 Ec (Electrical Conductivity)

EC of the STP water (1778 $\mu\text{s/cm}$) is found highest, showing the high concentration of ions in it, whereas the ground water had showed (6.94 $\mu\text{s/cm}$) lowest electric conductivity, showing the low concentration of ions in it. According to WHO, EC values of drinking water should be below or up to 400 $\mu\text{s/cm}$. EC of canal water (261 $\mu\text{s/cm}$) is found higher than the pond water (154.4 $\mu\text{s/cm}$) that is due to the long distance of pond from the industrial sludge than the canal (about 75 meters away from the disposed sludge). However canal and pond water, both adhere the permissible limits of EC for drinking as well as irrigation water. Increased EC values of STP and Canal water are showing the direct effect of industrial wastes on the water as shown in Table 1 and Fig. 5. Pond is open and 3 km away from the industrial area and it get contaminated due to domestic sewage, animals and pollutants. EC values of ground water, pond water and canal water are in the range suggested by WHO. So if cattle drink this water, it may not be harmful to them regarding EC issues. But high TDS, K, Fe, and Na levels of ground water can't be ignored.

1.3.3 TDS (Total Dissolved Salts)

TDS (3800 mg/L) and TS (3804 mg/L) of ground water were found very high. STP water had also showed higher TDS (1109 mg/L) and total solids values (1346 mg/L) but lower than ground water as shown in Table 1 and Fig.2.. Canal water adjacent to industrial sludge had showed greater values of TDS (168 mg/L) and total solids (186 mg/L) than the pond water. The high values of TDS and total solids reflects the greater concentration of ions in canal water than the pond water. Permissible limit of TDS for drinking purpose is 500 mg/L (IS- 10500, 2012) and TDS greater than 2000 mg/L is unsuitable for irrigation purpose (FAQ 2006). Ground water TDS (3800 mg/L) was found much greater than the recommended limits and do not comply with the standard limits of drinking and irrigation water. TDS of STP water adhere to the permissible limit of irrigation water.

1.3.4 Total Suspended Solids & Total Solids

Total suspended solids were reported highest in STP water (237 mg/L) followed by canal water (18 mg/L) followed by pond water (14 mg/L). It was found less than 5 mg/L in ground water. STP water contains many treated industries effluents that consist of many suspended solids in it. Canal is passing side by the disposed sludge, its TSS concentration is due to nearby sludge. Total solids follows the order i.e. ground water (3804 mg/L) > STP water (1346mg/L) > canal water (186 mg/L) > pond water (116 mg/L) as shown in Table 1 and Fig.7.

1.3.5 Na (Sodium)

Sodium content in water samples follow the order, STP water (182 mg/kg) > ground water (96 mg/kg) > canal water (12 mg/kg) > pond water (9 mg/kg) as shown in Table 1 and Fig. 3. Sewage treatment plant water is rich in sodium content, that is due to various chemicals and materials used in industries. Higher concentration of Na in ground water can be correlated to leaching of various ions through soil and reaches to ground water. Adequate amount of Na is required in human body but it is not considered as an essential element for plant growth. It could be beneficial for growth of algae and cyanobacteria (Allen and Arnon 1955). Previous studies had reported the adverse effect of Na ion on nutrient uptake, transport and accumulation of nutrient ions. Tavakkoli et al 2010 had observed the diminished potassium and calcium ion nutrition in salinity treated bean plants. Ground water and STP water are found rich in sodium concentration. It can be inferred that STP water should be further treated to reduce its sodium concentration, before its application as irrigation water.

1.3.6 K (Potassium)

Ground water had showed highest concentration of K (51 mg/L), which is above the permissible limit (12 mg/kg) as per WHO guidelines. Drinking of this ground water may cause diseases related to exceeded level of potassium. It was not found in pond and canal water, however STP water had reported little amount of K (0.75 mg/L) as shown in Table 1. Negative effect of sodium, potassium and magnesium on soil hydraulic properties were reported by C. J. Smith et al 2014. Their damaging effects were observed to follow the order Na > K > Mg. (C. J. Smith et al). Irrigation with potassium and sodium rich water could alter the soil hydraulic properties of soil.

1.3.7 Nitrates

STP water was found rich in nitrates (44 mg/L) followed by ground water (42 mg/L). Lower values of nitrates was reported in canal (0.68 mg/L) and pond water (0.72 mg/L) as shown in Table 1 and Fig. 8. Nitrates concentration in ground water and STP water meets the Indian standards for irrigation water. Plants require nitrates and phosphate in good amount for proper growth. Appreciable amount of nitrates and phosphates in STP water and ground water makes them suitable for irrigation but values of other parameters should also be taken in consideration.

1.3.8 Phosphates and Magnesium

STP and ground water are rich in phosphate, whereas the canal water and pond water had shown the almost similar values of phosphate. STP water (81 mg/L) showed the highest amount of phosphate followed by ground water (75 mg/L) followed by canal (1.3 mg/L). and pond water (1.2 mg/L). High concentrations of phosphates could be a factor for depletion of dissolved oxygen in water sources and degrade the water quality and also indicates the presence of pollutants in water. (WHO, 1993). According to WHO 1993 Standards, permissible amount of phosphate is 0.3 mg/L. Ground water had reported very high concentration of phosphate, it is matter of concern and indicates the contamination in it.

Magnesium was not found in the Ground water, canal water and pond water but very little amount of Mg was found in STP water.

1.3.9 Fe (Iron)

Fe concentration follows the order STP water (2.2 mg/L) > ground water (1.27 mg/L) > canal water (1.0 mg/L) > pond water (0.96 mg/L). According to WHO guidelines for drinking water, permissible limit of Fe is 0.3 mg/kg as shown in Table 1 and Fig. 4.. Water of all four sampling sites shows high concentration of iron. This shows direct influence of industrial wastes and pollution on the water quality. It is very surprising to see the higher concentration of iron in ground water, which makes it unfit for drinking purpose. However all the studied water samples were found to adhere to recommended permissible limit of iron for irrigation water i.e. 5.0 mg/L.

1.4 CONCLUSIONS

TDS of ground water is found very high (3800 mg/L) as compared to the standard permissible limit for drinking purpose (500 mg/L) and irrigation purpose (2000 mg/L). It is rich in iron concentration (1.27 mg/L), which is above the permissible range (0.3 mg/L) for drinking purpose but comply with the standard limits for irrigation water. Potassium content (51 mg/L) in ground water is also above the permissible limit as per WHO (12 mg/L) guidelines. Ground water and STP water were found rich in sodium concentration. Ground water had reported high concentration of phosphate (75 mg/L), which is too much higher than the permissible limits (0.3 mg/L) as per WHO guidelines 1993. It is matter of concern and indicates the increased degree of contamination in it. Out of the four sampling sites, TDS and Total solids had showed highest values in ground water. It could be inferred that ground water of this area is unsafe for drinking purpose, however it was not found too much harmful for irrigation purpose but the enhanced TDS value, higher potassium concentration, higher values of phosphate and increased concentration of Na cannot be ignored. This deteriorated quality of ground water could be correlated with the industrial influence on it. pH of all the four sampling sites were found within the range as per WHO guidelines. STP water had showed pH (8.0) TDS values (1109 mg/L), TS (1346 mg/L), concentration of K (0.75 mg/L), Fe (2.2 mg/L) and good amount of nitrates (44 mg/L). All these parameters are comply with the permissible limits of irrigation water. Out of four sampling sites, only STP water had showed a little amount of Magnesium. This water had also reported highest value of EC, which shows the presence of various ions in it. STP water could be good alternative for irrigation water in this era of scarcity of irrigation water. But increased level of EC, phosphate and sodium in STP water could impart adverse effect on the crops. As increased phosphates can alter the soil pH and promotes the algae growth. It is an essential nutrient for the plants but too much higher value can alter the production of crops. So STP water should be further treated to reduce the level of EC, phosphate and Sodium in it. Canal water adjacent to industrial wastes is further found more contaminated than the pond water. EC of canal water (261 $\mu\text{s}/\text{cm}$) is found to be higher than the pond water (154.4 $\mu\text{s}/\text{cm}$). All the measured parameters of canal water had showed greater values than pond water and comply with the standards of drinking water but increased concentration of iron (above the permissible limit for drinking purpose) in both the samples could be due to contamination of these water sources. As canal is about 75 meters away from the sludge, is found more contaminated than pond water. Now except Fe, all the parameters of canal and pond water are within the range as per WHO guidelines for drinking water, but if contamination persists, it would be a serious threat to living beings. Direct influence of industrial wastes on the water quality can be seen here on the ground water, canal water and pond water, but the ground water is found more unsuitable for drinking as well as irrigation. Further concentration of heavy metal in these water sources should be inferred before reaching to any conclusion.

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AUTHOR DETAILS:**PUSHPA YADAV¹, SOUVANIK TALUKDAR², SOMA SHARMA³ AND ANOOP YADAV⁴**¹KLP College, Rewari, Raffles University, Neemrana²Raffles University, Neemrana³RPSDC, Balana, M. Garh, Haryana⁴CUH, Haryana